

The bell at dpa'-ris

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In 2010,a new Tibetan inscription of bell was found at dpa'-ris,. dPa'-ris Autonomous County is located in the south of Wuwei city, Gansu province (northwest of China). During the period of Tang Dynasty

(618-907) and Song Dynasty(960-1279), Wu wei was called Liangzhou in Chinese , in 1246 centuries Sa-skya *pantita* , a famous scholar and leader of Tibetan Buddhism Sa-skya tradition , arrived at Liangzhou to meet the Mongol prince Go-tan, grandson of Genghis Khan. Their talks led to the establishment of political ties between Tibetan and Mongol royal house.

The inscription of the bell in three lines runs round and the text has been published by Lha mchog skybs, who is a professor of northwest nationalities University in Lanzhou, and photographs of the bell can be seen in *Bod ljongs zhib 'jug* (Tibetan studies), no.1,2011.

Tibetan inscription

Bod kyi lha btsan po khri gtsug lde brtsan mched kyi sku yon du bsngo
ste zhang rgya sgra rgyal slebs spad kyi Jag-rong dga'-ldan byin cen
gtsug lag khang gi rkyen du dril chen cik pul ba'I yon kyi yon bdag dang
sems can thams cad bla na myed de byang cub kyi ryub bar smon to/
drill 'di lcags kong gis yi ge bri ste dge slong chos prin gyis blugso/

Translation

As a religious for the god, btsan-po of Tibet, khri gtsug lde brtsan and his
brother, The zhang lha sgra rgyal slebs spad made and offer this big bell

to the Jag-rong dga'-ldan byin cen gtsug lag khang, in order to wish Donor and all living beings will be perfected in the highest enlightenment. The inscription of bell was written by lcags kong, it was cast by *dge slong* (monks who have taken the highest monastic vows)chos-prin.

The inscription shows that the bell was made for Jag-rong dga' ldan byin cen gtsug lag khang, at liang zhou region at the time of the king, Khri gtsug lde brtsan's edict of 704-755A.D.

According to histories, During the time of king Khri gtsug lde brtsan, Tibetan forces often engaged in the war with Tang Dynast in this region. From 764 to 848, Tibetan force occuoation of Liangzhou lasted 82 years.

Now there are still some questions to be need discuss:

- 1) what was the history background of the bell?
- 2) How to spread the Tibetan Buddhism in Liangzhou region during the first half of 8 century?
- 3) Who was *dge slong* Chos prin(sprin)? Tibetan Buddhist monk or Chinese Buddhist monk? If he was a Tibetan *dge slong* , How to explain to appear Tibetan monk before the time when bsam-yas gtsug lag khang was set up ?